

Patient Delays in Interventional Radiology

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Background

- Delays result in increased length of hospital stay, repeat surgeries, readmissions, additional medical visits, increased follow-up care, medical errors, or rushed procedures and unsafe practices.
- Delays impact
 - Healthcare facilities
 - Patients
 - Staff
- In surgical units the first case of the day is tracked for inefficiencies due to the rippling effect for subsequent cases

Purpose

- Increase the causative factors for delays by creating evidenced-based practice tools
 - Flow Map
 - Intake Form
 - Checklist
- Identify causes of delays with new intake form 40%

Framework

Model for Improvement

Methods

- Pre/ post QI project Design
- Pre-intervention period – Sept – Nov 2021 & 6 cases in Dec 2021; N=64
- Post-intervention period – Dec – Feb 2022; N=49
- QI project introduced Sept 2021
- Educational/ training session in Dec

PDSA Cycle Set 1.0

- Weekly meetings
- Multidisciplinary Team Approach
- Implemented new intake form

PDSA Cycle Set 2.0

- Bi-Weekly meetings
- Multidisciplinary Team Approach
- First working RADPASS created
- Scheduling checklist created

Findings

Pre-intervention

- Total first case late starts (FCLS)= 55
- First cases started on time= 16%
- FCLS w/o documented delay reason= 83%, N=39

Post-intervention

- Total first case late starts (FCLS)= 33
- First cases started on time= 27%
- FCLS w/o documented delay reason= 32%, N=13
- 2,594 total minutes delayed; 43 hours

QI project helped increase teamwork, communication, safety practices, and quality of care by pinpointing inefficiencies in IRSU

Reason for First Case Late Start	Documented Pre (Sep-Nov)	Documented Post (Dec-Feb)
Labs		3
Patient Late or No Show		1
Morning Huddle		1
Patient Not Ready in SSU	4	17
IR called for 8:30 or later		2
No Reason Documented	39	13
Medical		3
Canceled	3	1
Weight	1	
Called For @		820-830

First Case Delayed Minutes	Pre (Sep-Nov)	Post (Dec-Feb)
< 15	14 (29%)	12 (31%)
15-30	23 (47%)	14 (36%)
30-60	11 (22%)	9 (23%)
>60	1 (2%)	4 (10%)

Intake Form

RADPASS- Checklist

Limitations/Recommendations

Limitations

- Short project timeline
- Hawthorne Effect
- Staff buy-in resistance
- Unable to calculate exact delay cost

Recommendations

- Call for first case earlier
- Create a digital or other check-in process in SSU to track first cases/ IRSU patients